

Species 1: *H. erato*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.65; high PNT

NOT test

Species 2: *H. charitonia*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.44; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red= $S1 > S2$, Blue= $S1 < S2$, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.323

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.017$

Background 2→1

D
p.value = 0.0050

Background 1→2

D
p.value = 0.0021

Species 1: *H. erato*

NDT test

Species 2: *H. charitonia*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.24

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

